

Design Application Number:

6406898

Filing Date (Provisional):

24 November 2024

Defer Registration:

No

Design Title:

Omni-Channel Retail Workforce Platform with Artificial Intelligence Assistant

Additional Description:

A graphical user interface for workforce management comprising:

- An integrated artificial intelligence assistant.
- Dynamic data visualization components.
- Interactive communication modules.
- Voice command capabilities.